

Digital Competence Centre

Strategy 2025-2028

Version 1.1

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Summary

The TU Delft Digital Competence Centre (DCC) elevates research across all research domains, faculties, and career stages with expertise in data management, research software development, and computational workflows. Since its launch in September 2020, the DCC has doubled in size and supported over 60 research projects across all faculties, delivering tailored, hands-on contributions that drive scientific excellence.

Strategic ambitions

1. Implement a tiered service model to support researchers at key stages of the research lifecycle and connect with local ambassadors to integrate DCC services into research workflows.
2. Enable grant-funded support roles to increase central capacity and facilitate establishing faculty embedded staff through a hub-and-spoke model.
3. Collaborate closely with central units and cultivate a community of practice to ensure seamless support and shared learning across the institution.

This strategy balances proven hands-on impact with scalable, sustainable models, ensuring TU Delft researchers have timely, trusted digital support for groundbreaking science.

1 Introduction

1.1 Looking back

The TU Delft Digital Competence Centre was established in September 2020. As a strategic partnership between the ICT Department and the Library, and with start-up funding from the TU Delft Open Science Program¹, we piloted addressing a growing need for hands-on support in research data management and software development.

At the start, the DCC consisted of four Research Software Engineers, two Data Managers and a project manager. Soon after, the DCC Co-ordinator was appointed and the DCC steering committee was established.

With the already established network of faculty data stewards at TU Delft, we complemented the available support by offering active collaboration in research projects. By collaborating directly with researchers, we aimed to embed digital competences within research groups through co-developing solutions. Over this five-year period, we have successfully supported researchers in over 60 projects across the TU Delft faculties, demonstrating a clear need for the support offered by the DCC.

Recognizing that the availability and reach of a central team is limited, we actively sought additional ways to make our growing expertise more accessible to researchers. We implemented a workflow to test and adopt new initiatives in our portfolio, through which we expanded our services to include Office Hours, a mentoring program, and curated resources and guides.

1.1.1 Funding

From the national strategic agenda for the digitalization in science² and the subsequent three investments rounds in local DCCs from NWO and Open Science NL³, the national programme that aims to accelerate the transition to open science, funding was made available to establish and strengthen DCC's within knowledge institutions.

Through both national funding and institutional recognition, the team has grown to eight Research Software Engineers and four Research Data Engineers (formerly Data Managers), becoming an established support service.

1.1.2 Key lessons learned

- Hands-on project support is an effective model to support research, learn about the needs and challenges *from researchers*, and grow the expertise of the team.
- Consider scalability of our services and address common needs through collective approaches.
- Balance DCC availability for short questions and long-term commitments.

¹ TU Delft Strategic Plan Open Science 2020-2024, <https://doi.org/10.4233/uuid:f2faff07-408f-4cec-bd87-0919c9e4c26f>

² Integrale aanpak voor digitalisering in de wetenschap, [Uitvoeringsplan investeringen digitale onderzoeksinfrastructuur.pdf](#)

³ NWO funding for Local DCCs, <https://www.nwo.nl/en/researchprogrammes/implementation-plan-investments-digital-research-infrastructure>

1.2 Looking forward

1.2.1 Digital skills

As digital tools and methods become increasingly integral to research, the demand for (advanced) digital competencies continues to grow. Researchers are expected to adopt new technologies, yet their primary focus remains on conducting research, not becoming experts in every tool or method. A recurring question we hear is: *Which digital skills should researchers develop themselves, and which require specialized support?*

There is no one-size-fits-all answer. The appropriate balance between researcher capabilities and professional support depends on the domain, the scale of research ambitions, and the complexity of the tools involved. It is therefore important to offer flexible pathways for skill development and support, ranging from training for foundational skills to hands-on support for more advanced needs.

1.2.2 Rising demand in AI and Machine Learning

One notable area of growing interest is in artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML). Researchers are increasingly exploring these technologies to gain new insights, optimize processes, or analyse large and complex datasets. Supporting this shift requires dedicated expertise, not only in model development and deployment, but also in ensuring responsible, reproducible, and FAIR-aligned AI practices.

1.2.3 Governance and funding

Sustainable funding remains a challenge. National budget cuts to education and research funding in 2025 have created uncertainty around long-term planning. The DCC relies on a mix of funding sources:

1. TU Delft central university services through the ICT Department and the Library (first income stream)
2. NWO grant funding specific to the strengthening local DCCs, endorsed by the TU Delft Executive Board (second income stream)
3. TU Delft strategic programmes such as the Open Science Programme (first income stream)
4. Funding via research grants (second/third income stream)

More opportunities are now emerging for research grants to cover professional staff costs, as funders are increasingly allowing such expenses in their budgets⁴. While these developments are promising, they also raise practical challenges: recruiting and retaining highly skilled staff in a competitive job market remains difficult.

1.2.4 Strategic alignment

As we plan for the next phase of the DCC, we align our strategy with both TU Delft's **Digital Strategy** and the **National Open Science Program**. TU Delft envisions a research environment where:

⁴ Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability, <https://adore.software/declaration/>

“Discussion over digital methodologies flourishes in communities of practice supported by an extended competence center with expert research support to enable ground-breaking & innovative research with sustainable societal impact.”

From the Digital Strategy, initiatives such as the Integrated Research Services, which aim to connect university research services, and the Research Portal, which aims to provide a central portal, are being implemented.

At the national level, the Open Science Program⁵ sets a clear direction for the future:

“In 2030, all research based on the use of research software (including data, publications, methods, and analyses) is transparent, verifiable, reproducible, and reusable. Both research and support staff are recognized and rewarded for their active involvement in the development, maintenance, and application of research software.”

This statement affirms the importance of roles like Research Software and Data Engineers and underscores the need for sustained investment in professional support infrastructure.

⁵ Open Science 2030 in the Netherlands, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>

2 Strategic positioning

2.1 Who are we?

The TU Delft Digital Competence Centre is a centralized team dedicated to supporting the adoption of best practices for data management and software development. We champion open science and FAIR principles by actively engaging with researchers across all university faculties. Our Research Software Engineers (RSE) and Research Data Engineers (RDE) take pride in contributing to TU Delft's digital excellence.

We value:

- Delivering high-quality work through our expertise
- Co-creating solutions with researchers
- Sharing knowledge
- Advancing trustworthy and open science

2.1.1 Our mission

We elevate research across all research domains, faculties, and career stages with expertise in data management, research software development, and computational workflows.

2.2 Our position

The DCC has a centralized place among the available support services at TU Delft. Through ICT and the Library, we can connect researchers with available expertise on research infrastructure and data management. To connect with researchers, we rely on the network of Faculty Data Stewards, our network of supported researchers, and local professional staff.

Nationally, we contribute to TDCC-NES, a national initiative coordinated by NWO that addresses shared challenges in data and software management across the Natural & Engineering Sciences. We also take part in NL-RSE, the community of research software engineers in the Netherlands, which promotes recognition, knowledge exchange, and sustainable career paths for RSEs.

3 Our ambition

3.1 Vision

At the TU Delft Digital Competence Centre, we envision a research environment where digital expertise is foundational to trustworthy, reproducible and impactful science. We aspire to be a driving force in shaping a culture of open, collaborative, and digitally driven science.

This strategy focuses our efforts by consolidating proven ways of working and introducing strategic improvements in visibility and sustainability. It is built around three complementary ambitions:

1. Ensuring the DCC is a well-known, trusted, and accessible partner
2. Expanding research support capacity through funded services and strengthening long-term support structures
3. Connecting and aligning the DCC within a wider support ecosystem

3.2 Ambition 1 – DCC is a well-known, trusted, and accessible research support partner

The DCC has offered hands-on project support as its core service through yearly calls for 5 years. While this support has proven effective, its near full-time engagement limits our visibility and accessibility to researchers with other queries.

To extend our reach, the DCC has been piloting new initiatives including Open Office Hours, mentoring through the FAIR for Research Software program, and DCC Guides. These services and resources help decouple our availability from the yearly call cycle and allow us to provide tailored support for specific queries.

GOAL: INCREASE DCC'S VISIBILITY, TRUST, AND ACCESSIBILITY THROUGH A TIERED SUPPORT MODEL

We will structure our existing services into progressive tiers, ranging from self-service resources and consultations to hands-on project collaborations, enabling researchers to access the right level of help when they need it. Our aim is to provide targeted support on data management and software development at key stages of the research life cycle, from grant writing through execution to publication, complementing existing research services. By offering multiple, clearly defined ways to engage with the DCC, we will reduce barriers to entry, increase our accessibility, and build trust through timely, relevant support.

At the same time, the DCC is not equipped to serve as a first-line helpdesk and will continue to rely on partnerships with other university support services and curated online resources to route queries appropriately.

Our hands-on project support remains the cornerstone of our services as it has a proven impact on research quality and contributes to building our expertise. Staffing and resource allocation will therefore consider not only the number of supported researchers but also take the broader impact and long-term value of the service into account. By combining our hands-on support with more accessible entry points, we will increase our accessibility and overall impact.

As a central organisation, the DCC benefits from close internal ties to ICT and the Library and maintains an outward-facing role through collaborations with other DCC's and (inter)national networks. However, a challenge of this centralised model is our limited visibility at the level of the faculty or department. While community events and central outreach engage a subset of motivated researchers, they often do not reach the broader research community.

GOAL: STRENGTHEN LOCAL PRESENCE TO BUILD VISIBILITY AND TRUST ACROSS THE UNIVERSITY

Through our hands-on project support, we have built a strong network of researchers who have benefited from our services firsthand. This group, ranging from PhD candidates to principal investigators, is well positioned to act as ambassadors for the DCC within their community.

We will actively engage with this network to share their experiences and promote awareness of the DCC's offerings and the best practices we support. By participating in local meetings, seminars, and informal events, we aim to make our support more visible and accessible. Peer-to-peer sharing tends to resonate more strongly and can lead to broader adoption and recognition of the role data and software in research.

In parallel, we will collaborate with faculty leadership, data stewards, and other professional staff to embed DCC services into established institutional workflows, such as research proposal development, onboarding processes, and data and software management planning. Ensuring our services are visible at key moments across the research lifecycle will help researchers discover and benefit from our support when it matters.

3.3 Ambition 2 – Expand research support capacity through funded services and strengthen long-term support structures

The DCC is currently funded by ICT and the Library, with occasional funding from external sources such as the NWO. This stable, centrally funded model has enabled us to offer core services free of charge, lowering the barrier to access, and supporting the adoption of open science and FAIR principles across TU Delft.

While this structure has helped secure permanent staff positions and embed the DCC within the university, it lacks the flexibility needed to scale with growing and evolving demand. At the same time, new opportunities are emerging for researchers to request project-based funding for dedicated research support roles, such as Research Software Engineers and Research Data Engineers. To meet this evolving landscape, a more flexible funding model is needed to address the growing demand for support.

GOAL: INTRODUCE FUNDED PROJECT SUPPORT AS A SERVICE TO EXPAND CAPACITY

We will introduce a funded, hands-on project support service as a complementary layer to our centrally funded work. Researchers can allocate project funding to receive dedicated support from DCC staff. This approach will allow us to scale capacity more flexibly and respond to specific research needs, while maintaining our centrally funded services as the stable foundation of the DCC.

In line with Ambition 1, we will also provide support during the grant preparation phase, helping researchers align project goals with our expertise and secure funding for the necessary support roles. This early involvement ensures that digital support is planned from the outset, improving project outcomes and sustainability.

Crucially, this expansion will not compromise our core values. We will retain our independent, collaborative approach and avoid shifting towards a commercial service provider model. The funded support will serve as a complementary layer within our portfolio, rather than a replacement for our existing project support. The funds will be deployed to extend capacity, not to cover existing central funding.

While project-based funding offers valuable opportunities to expand research support, it also presents challenges, particularly in retaining expertise within TU Delft. Most roles funded through individual projects are limited in scope and duration, often resulting in part-time contracts with limited long-term security. This undermines the continuity of support and restricts the retention of institutional knowledge. At the same time, there is growing recognition that sustainable, long-term support for digital skills is essential to advancing open and innovative research.

GOAL: SUPPORT ESTABLISHING LONG-TERM FACULTY/DEPARTMENTAL PROFESSIONAL STAFF

To address these challenges, we will support the establishment of embedded support staff within faculties and departments. These local professional staff, preferably organised in teams, are better positioned to respond to the specific needs of their research communities, whether through domain expertise or specialized tooling.

We will adopt a hub-and-spoke model, in which the DCC serves as a central hub providing strategic coordination, expertise, and community-building, while local support teams act as spokes, offering tailored services aligned with the needs of their specific research environments. This model promotes consistency in quality and best practices across TU Delft, while enabling local flexibility and depth.

This decentralization is not at odds with the growth of central DCC services through a grant-funded model. Complementary to local support, the DCC will continue to offer hands-on support as a core service, ensuring that all researchers at TU Delft, regardless of their discipline, have access to high-quality expertise.

We will work closely with existing local teams and staff, such as the Research Engineering and Infrastructure Team (REIT) at the faculty of EEMCS, building on existing business cases and practical experience, to guide departments in developing similar models. A key priority in this effort is advocating for institutional commitment to permanent positions for research support staff.

Long-term contracts are essential for ensuring continuity, retaining expertise, and enabling sustained development of skills, services, and institutional memory. As part of this effort, we will prioritize faculties and departments that have expressed a need and where DCC support is already substantial, working with them to determine the appropriate scale and structure of local teams.

3.4 Ambition 3 – Connect and align research support staff

Across TU Delft, several central support teams contribute to a shared mission through the TU Delft Digital Strategy. However, these services are still fragmented despite sharing common goals. For the DCC to be truly findable, effective, and impactful, it is essential that we strengthen connection and alignment across central support services. This ambition aligns closely with the goals outlined in the TU Delft Digital Strategy, which calls for a more coherent and user-centred support ecosystem.

GOAL: CONNECT AND ALIGN DCC WITH CENTRAL SUPPORT SERVICES

We will contribute to a more unified central research support offering, starting with better integration of DCC services with the available support on data management through the Faculty Data Stewards. The DCC will also play an active role in shaping the training offering for researchers through the Library, ensuring our contributions are grounded in practical experience with data and software-intensive research. To offer our support on grant applications within the funded project support, we will ensure alignment with existing support through the Innovation & Impact Center. The DCC cannot succeed in isolation, only through aligned efforts across TU Delft can we achieve a truly integrated research support system.

We are well positioned to act as a connector and our ongoing engagement with researchers across disciplines offers a broad view of emerging needs and remaining challenges. At the same time, our involvement in national networks and communities strengthens our ability to align with broader developments and advocate for TU Delft's needs at the national level.

By adopting the proposed hub-and-spokes model, we can facilitate the onboarding, training, and networking of local support staff, ensuring they have the required tools and knowledge. However, true sustainability requires more than structural alignment and depends on a connected, well-supported community.

GOAL: STRENGTHEN A COMMUNITY OF EXPERTISE AT TU DELFT AND BEYOND

We will contribute to strengthening a network of research software and data professionals with TU Delft and across the national landscape by sharing practices, aligning quality standards, and promoting professional development. This includes organizing events and knowledge-sharing sessions where we can share and discuss lessons learned and showcase successful practices.

Building from our internal knowledge-sharing sessions, we will help create an open environment where research software and data professionals can exchange ideas, discuss challenges, and learn from one another as part of a broader, collaborative community of practice.

4 People and organisation

We are an **open, versatile, and independent** team of research support professionals, committed to building an inspiring environment that responds to evolving demands of digital research. We value our adaptive nature to support research with the latest technological developments.

One of our key strengths is the cultural and disciplinary diversity within our team. With a wide range of technical and scientific backgrounds, we are well positioned to collaborate effectively across the scientific domains at TU Delft.

To remain effective and relevant, we are addressing several challenges related to capacity and workload:

- **Team sustainability:** We focus on building and sustaining a skilled, motivated team by offering career development opportunities, fostering a supportive learning environment, and advocating for long-term contracts to safeguard expertise and institutional knowledge. ⁶
- **Specialization opportunities:** We are developing areas of specialization that enable team members to deepen expertise in ways that align with the evolving needs of researcher.
- **Room for individual impact:** Each team member brings unique interests and strengths. We encourage autonomy and support professional growth so that everyone can make meaningful contributions aligned with their passions and skills.

4.1 Professional development

Our greatest asset is the knowledge and experience of the team members. They have built strong relationships with researchers, actively share their knowledge, and contribute to a culture of collaboration and continuous learning. One example is our *Coding Sessions*, which enable the exchange of skills and experiences within our team and with other professional staff. These sessions provide a space to share project successes and challenges, and to explore new tools and practices.

As digital research support continues to mature, professional development is a key priority at both institutional and national levels. At TU Delft, we are committed to creating transparent and supportive career paths for RSEs and RDEs. This includes:

- Advocating for equal opportunities and recognition for professional staff at TU Delft
- Updating relevant job profiles to reflect evolving responsibilities
- Aligning professional growth with career development trajectories

Recognizing the growing trend towards embedded research support roles, the DCC actively contributes to national efforts to professionalize these roles⁶, including the development of a new UFO profile that better captures the hybrid research and support functions of RDEs and RSEs.

⁶ Professionalizing the role of Research Software Engineers in the Netherlands, <https://zenodo.org/records/15052095>

4.2 Expertise

The expertise of the DCC is organized around 5 domains:

- Data management
- Data analytics
- Software development
- Software quality
- Computational workflows

These domains form the foundation of the support we provide to researchers across TU Delft. While centralized, we acknowledge an existing demand for domain-specific expertise close to researchers. With the incorporation of grant-funded support, we can align support more closely with the needs of research groups, either through DCC capacity or through faculty- or department-level support structures.

4.2.1 Non-technical skills

Our effectiveness as a support team is not based on technical expertise alone. Non-technical skills are essential to building trust, navigating complex projects, and enabling successful collaborations. The responsibilities of the team often extend beyond solving technical problems and include communication, stakeholder management, adaptability, and project management.

Team members regularly engage with researchers from diverse disciplines, requiring the ability to translate between technical and domain-specific languages. Skills such as active listening and negotiation help ensure that researchers feel heard and supported throughout their projects.

We actively foster the development of these skills through peer mentoring and training opportunities.⁷ By valuing both technical and non-technical capabilities, we strengthen our role as trusted partners in research.

⁷ Introduction to (Research) Software Project Management, <https://zenodo.org/records/15058230>

5 Support model

We aim to provide a tiered portfolio of services that supports researchers throughout the research life cycle, from grant writing to publication, on topics of data management and software development. This model reflects our ambition to be a versatile and reliable partner in digital research support.

5.1 Hands-on project support

From the outset, hands-on project support has been the core service of the DCC. Researchers apply for this support through an annual call, and successful applicants are matched with DCC staff who embed directly into research teams on a part-time basis for a defined period. This model enables us to co-develop digital research solutions, gain insight into practical challenges, and grow our expertise across disciplines. The support is offered in kind to encourage and support the adoption of open science and FAIR practices.

5.2 Funded hands-on project support

To increase support capacity and respond more flexibly to demand, we aim to incorporate a grant-funded support model. This requires updates to our current service while preserving core principles (see insert).

As research funders increasingly recognize the value of digital research support, more grants now include options to budget for RSEs and RDEs. To align with this trend, we are introducing a funded support model in which DCC staff can collaborate on externally funded research projects, within our areas of expertise and available capacity. With this model, our time is (partly) covered by research funding, introducing a new income stream.

This stream, complementing our central funding, allows more flexibility to expand our capacity by hiring new staff. This approach offers several benefits:

- Researchers receive early feedback on the feasibility of digital components in grant proposals.
- Projects benefit from collaboration with experienced staff who are embedded in the TU Delft research ecosystem, instead of relying on newly recruited (temporary) staff.
- The need for time-consuming recruitment processes is reduced.
- Sustained, funded engagement supports long-term staff retention and builds institutional knowledge.

Importantly, it is not intended to turn the DCC into a software development service. Rather, we act as collaborative partners, offering technical expertise that strengthens research outcomes.

CORE PRINCIPLES

Collaborative development - We work closely with researchers to co-design and co-develop solutions. The DCC does not assume sole responsibility for all development tasks within a project. Instead, we actively collaborate with researchers to achieve their goals.

Knowledge transfer – Through our hands-on support, we take the opportunity to transfer digital skills and knowledge to researchers. As we cannot maintain the solution we co-develop, researchers need to be actively involved in the project and take responsibility for maintaining the developed solutions after support completion.

Open and FAIR - In line with TU Delft’s Research Software and Data Policies, we aim to publish solutions as open source where appropriate, and whenever possible, we prioritize the re-use of existing data and software solutions.

Time-based commitment - During our support, we promise a time commitment based on the number of hours dedicated to the project.

To ensure a smooth and sustainable adoption of our funded project support model, we will introduce the service gradually through a transition period. This approach allows us to test, evaluate, and refine the model before scaling up. During this phase, we will take deliberate steps to manage risks:

- Select only funded proposals that clearly align with our expertise and available capacity
- Use a transparent and manageable intake process to allow workload distribution.
- Apply safeguards for multi-year projects, including review checkpoints and phased commitments.
- Prioritize team-based involvement to ensure continuity, redundancy, and shared expertise within each supported project.
- Create a clear distinction with our existing support.

Throughout the transition period, we will monitor outcomes and gather feedback from both researchers and DCC staff. Based on this evaluation, we will determine how to adjust or expand the service while protecting team capacity and ensuring long-term value.

5.3 Teaching

The DCC plays an active role in advancing research skills at TU Delft. While many of our teaching contributions have been voluntary and ad hoc, we are formalizing our involvement to create more structured and impactful learning opportunities. This also helps ensure that teaching is properly recognized as part of our professional work.

As instructors, helpers, and curriculum designers, we contribute to foundational training initiatives such as the Carpentries and CodeRefinery. Our close involvement in research projects gives us valuable insight into how training is applied in practice and where further learning is needed. A recurring observation is that while centrally offered courses provide a strong starting point, researchers benefit from more advanced, workflow-oriented follow-up training.

To address this, we are partnering with the Library Research Data Services Team and a dedicated software trainer to co-develop an intermediate-level training curriculum as part of a modular training program. This initiative will focus on enhancing researchers' ability to apply FAIR and open science principles in realistic research software scenarios.

Our FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) program has supported this goal by mentoring researchers as they move from learning basic skills to applying and adopting best practices in their own work.

5.4 Visibility

We strive to maintain a clear, accessible, and engaging presence to connect with researchers and stakeholders. Our approach includes:

- Maintaining an up-to-date website and resource guides to reflect current services and best practices.
- Collaborating with other university services to raise awareness of data and software support within faculties.
- Showcasing projects in partnership with the researchers we've supported, to demonstrate the value of good research practices. Featuring researchers helps demonstrate our impact through peer-to-peer insight.

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